

Vanishing functions with combinatorial coefficients

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Abstract: *This paper is devoted to some functions f_n of natural arguments which satisfy $f_n(j) = 0$ if $j \in \llbracket 0, n-1 \rrbracket$ or $f_n(j) = 0$ if $j \in \llbracket 1, n-1 \rrbracket$. The designed functions have been derived in a recent work [1] and involve some very well-known coefficients appearing in combinatorics.*

Notations: Throughout this manuscript, $c_{k,n}$ denotes the coefficient of x^k in the Taylor expansion of $\frac{x^{2n+1}}{\cosh^{2n+1} x}$ around 0; $d_{k,n}$ those of x^k in the Taylor expansion of $\frac{x^{2n}}{\cosh^{2n} x}$. $\langle m \rangle$ stands for Eulerian of type A; B_{2n} denotes Bernoulli numbers, $\langle n \rangle^B$ are Typ-B Eulerian numbers

Lemma 1 :

$$\forall n \in \mathbb{N}, \quad \sinh^{2n+1} z = \frac{1}{4^n} \sum_{k=0}^n (-1)^k \binom{2n+1}{k} \sinh(2n+1-2k)z$$

Proof :

On writing \sinh with its definition, one has

$$\sinh^{2n+1} w = \frac{1}{2^{2n+1}} (e^w - e^{-w})^{2n+1}$$

The Newton's binomial formula transforms the equality to this new one

$$\sinh^{2n+1} w = \frac{1}{2^{2n+1}} \sum_{k=0}^{2n+1} (-1)^k \binom{2n+1}{k} e^{(2n+1-2k)w}$$

The sum is then split into two as follow

$$\sinh^{2n+1} w = \frac{1}{2^{2n+1}} \left(\sum_{k=0}^n (-1)^k \binom{2n+1}{k} e^{(2n+1-2k)w} + \sum_{k=n+1}^{2n+1} (-1)^k \binom{2n+1}{k} e^{(2n+1-2k)w} \right)$$

On re-indexing the second sum to 0 and reversing the order of summation, we conclude

$$\sinh^{2n+1} w = \frac{1}{2^{2n+1}} \left(\sum_{k=0}^n (-1)^k \binom{2n+1}{k} e^{(2n+1-2k)w} - \sum_{k=0}^n (-1)^k \binom{2n+1}{k} e^{-(2n+1-2k)w} \right)$$

Which reads

$$\sinh^{2n+1} w = \frac{1}{4^n} \sum_{k=0}^n (-1)^k \binom{2n+1}{k} \sinh(2n+1-2k)w$$

Theorem 1:

$$\forall n \in \mathbb{N}^*, \quad \sum_{k=0}^n (-1)^k \binom{2n+1}{k} (2n+1-2k)^{2j+1} = \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if } j \in \llbracket 0, n-1 \rrbracket \\ 4^n (2n+1)!, & \text{if } j = n \end{cases}$$

Proof:

We prove the theorem by expanding $\cosh^{2n+1} z$ around $z_l := \frac{(2l+1)i\pi}{2}$ ($l \in \mathbb{Z}$) which are its zeros. We begin by setting $z := z_l + w$, since we are expanding around z_l

One has :

$$\cosh^{2n+1} z = \cosh^{2n+1}(z_l + w) = \underbrace{(\cosh z_l \cosh w + \sinh z_l \sinh w)}_0^{2n+1} = \sinh^{2n+1} z_l \sinh^{2n+1} w$$

Applying the equality given by *Lemma 1* yields

$$\cosh^{2n+1} z = \frac{1}{4^n} \sinh^{2n+1} z_l \sum_{k=0}^n (-1)^k \binom{2n+1}{k} \sinh(2n+1-2k)w$$

Since w approaches 0, a further expansion comes after using the Taylor expansion $\sinh w = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{w^{2n+1}}{(2n+1)!}$:

$$\cosh^{2n+1} z = \frac{1}{4^n} \sinh^{2n+1} z_l \sum_{k=0}^n (-1)^k \binom{2n+1}{k} \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \frac{(2n-2k+1)^{2j+1}}{(2j+1)!} w^{2j+1}$$

And after interchanging the summation operators

$$\cosh^{2n+1} z = \sinh^{2n+1} z_l \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \left[\frac{1}{4^n (2j+1)!} \sum_{k=0}^n (-1)^k \binom{2n+1}{k} (2n-2k+1)^{2j+1} \right] w^{2j+1}$$

The proof of the theorem emerges from remarking firstly that $g(z) := \frac{\cosh^{2n+1} z}{(z - z_l)^{2n+1} \sinh^{2n+1} z_l}$ is analytic around z_l because the numerator cancels the singularities at the denominator with the same multiplicity. Secondly, one sees trivially that

$$\lim_{z \rightarrow z_l} g(z) = 1$$

because the derivative of cosh is sinh. As first consequence,

$$\frac{1}{4^n(2n+1)!} \sum_{k=0}^n (-1)^k \binom{2n+1}{k} (2n-2k+1)^{2n+1} = 1$$

. On the second hand, it follows that the Taylor expansion of g around z_l is

$$1 + O(w)$$

It comes out that the series expansion of $\cosh^{2n+1} z$ around z_l is

$$\sinh^{2n+1} z_l w^{2n+1} + O(w^{2n+3})$$

Which means exactly that all coefficients of w^{2j+1} are 0 when $j < n$.

Theorem 2:

$$\forall n \geq 2, \quad \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} (-1)^k \binom{2n}{k} (2n-2k)^{2j} = \begin{cases} (-1)^{n+1} \binom{2n}{n}, & \text{if } j = 0 \\ 0, & \text{if } j \in \llbracket 1, n-1 \rrbracket \\ \frac{4^n(2n)!}{2}, & \text{if } j = n \end{cases}$$

Hint: The proof follows exactly the same line of reasoning sketched for Theorem 1. For instance, show first of all this formula by getting inspiration from proof of Lemma 1

$$\forall n \in \mathbb{N}^*, \quad \cosh^{2n} x = \frac{1}{4^n} \left[2 \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \binom{2n}{k} \cosh((2n-2k)x) + \binom{2n}{n} \right]$$

Theorem 3:

$$\forall n \in \mathbb{N}^*, \quad \sum_{m=0}^n c_{2m,n} \frac{1}{(2n-2m)!} (2k+1)^{2n-2m} = \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if } k \in \llbracket 0, n-1 \rrbracket \\ 4^n, & \text{if } k = n \end{cases}$$

Proof:

Let

$$M_{k,n} := \sum_{m=0}^n c_{2m,n} \frac{1}{(2n-2m)!} (2k+1)^{2n-2m},$$

$$y_{m,n} := c_{2m,n} \quad \text{and} \quad t_{m,k,n} := \frac{1}{(2m)!} (2k+1)^{2m}$$

Consequently,

$$M_{k,n} = \sum_{m=0}^n y_{m,n} t_{n-m,k,n}$$

We identify straightforward through this last form $M_{k,n}$ as the coefficient of x^n is the Cauchy product of the series generated by the coefficients $y_{m,n}$ and $t_{n-m,k,n}$ on the index m . On letting

$$Y_n(x) := \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} y_{m,n} x^m \quad T_{k,n}(x) := t_{m,k,n} x^m,$$

we write much more formally

$$M_{k,n} = [x^n] Y_n(x) T_{k,n}(x)$$

One has

$$Y_n(x) = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} y_{m,n} x^m = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} c_{2m,n} (\sqrt{x})^{2m} = \left(\frac{\sqrt{x}}{\sinh \sqrt{x}} \right)^{2n+1}$$

$$T_{k,n}(x) = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} t_{m,k,n} x^m = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(2m)!} (2k+1)^{2m} \sqrt{x}^{2m} = \cosh((2k+1)\sqrt{x})$$

It follows

$$M_{k,n} = [x^n] \left(\frac{\sqrt{x}}{\sinh \sqrt{x}} \right)^{2n+1} \cosh((2k+1)\sqrt{x})$$

On using the Cauchy integral formula, one gets

$$M_{k,n} = [x^n] \left(\frac{\sqrt{x}}{\sinh \sqrt{x}} \right)^{2n+1} \cosh((2k+1)\sqrt{x})$$

$$= \frac{1}{2\pi i} \oint_{|x|=\varepsilon} \frac{\left(\frac{\sqrt{x}}{\sinh \sqrt{x}} \right)^{2n+1} \cosh((2k+1)\sqrt{x})}{x^{n+1}} dx$$

The substitution $x = z^2$ yields

$$M_{k,n} = \frac{1}{\pi i} \oint_{|z|=\sqrt{\varepsilon}} \frac{\cosh((2k+1)z)}{(\sinh z)^{2n+1}} dz$$

On replacing sinh and cosh by their standard definitions, we obtain

$$M_{k,n} = \frac{2^{2n}}{\pi i} \oint_{|z|=\sqrt{\varepsilon}} \frac{e^{(2k+1)z} + e^{-(2k+1)z}}{(e^z - e^{-z})^{2n+1}} dz = \frac{2^{2n}}{\pi i} \oint_{|z|=\sqrt{\varepsilon}} \frac{e^{2(k+n+1)z} + e^{2(n-k)z}}{(e^{2z} - 1)^{2n+1}} dz$$

Which becomes following after the substitution $z = e^{2x}$

$$M_{k,n} = \frac{2^{2n-1}}{\pi i} \oint_{|x-1|=\delta} \frac{x^{k+n} + x^{n-k-1}}{(x-1)^{2n+1}} dx$$

On applying the formula, $f^{(m)}(a) = \frac{m!}{2\pi i} \oint_{\gamma} \frac{f(z)}{(z-a)^{m+1}} dz$, $M_{k,n}$ takes the form

$$M_{k,n} = \frac{2^{2n}}{(2n)!} \left. \frac{d^{2n}}{dx^{2n}} (x^{k+n} + x^{n-k-1}) \right|_{x=1}$$

We show easily here that none of powers $n + k$ and $n - k - 1$ is high enough to yield a nonzero $2n$ -th derivative when $k < n$. This means the right side vanishes when $k < n$.

This statement its turn implies that $\forall n \in \mathbb{N}^*$, the polynomial

$$P_n(x) := \sum_{m=0}^n c_{2m,n} \frac{1}{(2n - 2m)!} x^{2n-2m}$$

has roots at $1, 3, 5, \dots, 2n - 1$.

But the polynomial P_n is an even function because it is a linear combination of even functions (since $x \mapsto x^{2n-2m}$ is always even). This implies that $-x$ is a root of P_n if and only if x is a root. We conclude that the polynomial P_n has roots at $\pm 1, \pm 3, \pm 5, \dots, \pm 2n - 1$. They are exactly $2n$ roots for the polynomial. And something interesting, the polynomial P_n is a polynomial of degree $2n$ too (the highest degree been reached for $m = 0$). This means that the factorization of P_n is about all these roots. We write then :

$$\begin{aligned} P_n(x) &= s_n \prod_{k=-n}^{n-1} (x - (2k + 1)) \\ &= s_n \prod_{k=-n}^{-1} (x - (2k + 1)) \prod_{k=0}^{n-1} (x - (2k + 1)) \\ &= s_n \prod_{k=0}^{n-1} (x - (2(k - n) + 1)) \prod_{k=0}^{n-1} (x - (2k + 1)) \\ &= s_n \prod_{k=0}^{n-1} (x - (2(n - 1 - k - n) + 1)) \prod_{k=0}^{n-1} (x - (2k + 1)) \\ &= s_n \prod_{k=0}^{n-1} (x + (2k + 1)) \prod_{k=0}^{n-1} (x - (2k + 1)) \\ &= s_n \prod_{k=0}^{n-1} (x + (2k + 1)) (x - (2k + 1)) \\ &= s_n \prod_{k=0}^{n-1} (x^2 - (2k + 1)^2) \end{aligned}$$

Basic properties of polynomials allow to conclude that the coefficient s_n matches exactly those of x^{2n} , since it is the highest degree term. The identity $c_{0,n} = 1$ allows to conclude

$$s_n = \frac{1}{(2n)!}$$

And the closed form of the polynomial

$$P_n(x) = \frac{1}{(2n)!} \prod_{k=0}^{n-1} (x^2 - (2k + 1)^2)$$

An evaluation of $P_n(2n + 1)$ is proceeded as follow :

$$\begin{aligned}
 P_n(2n+1) &= \frac{1}{(2n)!} \prod_{k=0}^{n-1} \left((2n+1)^2 - (2k+1)^2 \right) \\
 &= \frac{1}{(2n)!} \prod_{k=0}^{n-1} (2n-2k)(2n+2k+2) \\
 &= \frac{1}{(2n)!} \prod_{k=0}^{n-1} 4(n-k)(n+k+1) \\
 &= \frac{4^n}{(2n)!} \prod_{k=0}^{n-1} (n-k)(n+k+1) \\
 &= \frac{4^n}{(2n)!} \prod_{k=0}^{n-1} (n-k) \prod_{k=0}^{n-1} (n+k+1) \\
 &= \frac{4^n}{(2n)!} \prod_{k=0}^{n-1} (k+1) \prod_{k=n+1}^{2n} k \\
 &= \frac{4^n}{(2n)!} n! \frac{\prod_{k=1}^{2n} k}{\prod_{k=1}^n k} \\
 &= \frac{4^n}{(2n)!} n! \frac{(2n)!}{n!} \\
 &= 4^n
 \end{aligned}$$

Lemma 2:

Let $f(x)$ be locally integrable on $(0, \infty)$ and assume its Mellin transform

$$\mathcal{M}[f](s) = \int_0^\infty f(x) x^{s-1} dx$$

admits a meromorphic continuation to a domain containing a vertical strip $\alpha < \Re(s) < \beta$. Then the asymptotic expansion of $f(x)$ as $x \rightarrow 0^+$ is determined by the poles of $\mathcal{M}[f](s)$:

$$f(x) \sim \sum_{s_0} \text{Res}_{s=s_0} \left(\mathcal{M}[f](s) x^{-s} \right), \quad x \rightarrow 0^+,$$

where the sum runs over the poles s_0 of $\mathcal{M}[f](s)$ in the half-plane $\Re(s) > \alpha$. Each simple pole of $\mathcal{M}[f](s)$ at $s = s_0$ contributes a term

$$c x^{-s_0}, \quad c = \text{Res}_{s=s_0} \mathcal{M}[f](s),$$

while a pole of order m contributes a term of the form

$$\left(\text{polynomial in } \log x \text{ of degree } m-1 \right) \cdot x^{-s_0}.$$

To find proves of this theorem, refer to [2] [3] [4] [5] [6] [7] [8] [9]

Theorem 4:

$$\forall n \in \mathbb{N}^*, \sum_{r=0}^{n-p} \frac{c_{2n-2p-2r,n}}{(2r)!} \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \left\langle \begin{matrix} 2n \\ n-1-k \end{matrix} \right\rangle (2k+1)^{2r} = \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if } p \in \llbracket 0, n-1 \rrbracket \\ \frac{(2n)!}{2}, & \text{if } p = n \end{cases}$$

We let first of all

$$g_{p,n} := \sum_{r=0}^{n-p} \frac{c_{2n-2p-2r,n}}{(2r)!} \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \left\langle \begin{matrix} 2n \\ n-1-k \end{matrix} \right\rangle (2k+1)^{2r}$$

Furthermore, we consider

$$y_{r,n} := c_{2r,n} \quad \text{and} \quad s_{r,n} := \frac{1}{(2r)!} \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \left\langle \begin{matrix} 2n \\ n-1-k \end{matrix} \right\rangle (2k+1)^{2r}$$

We become this,

$$g_{p,n} = \sum_{r=0}^{n-p} y_{n-p-r,n} s_{r,n}$$

This last formula is exactly the form taken by coefficients of the Cauchy product of two series. Hence, we read $g_{p,n}$ as the coefficient of x^{n-p} in the Cauchy-product of the two series generated by the coefficients $y_{r,n}$ and $s_{r,n}$.

We let

$$Y_n(x) := \sum_{r=0}^{\infty} y_{r,n} x^r \quad \text{and} \quad S_n(x) := \sum_{r=0}^{\infty} s_{r,n} x^r$$

More formally,

$$g_{p,n} = [x^{n-p}] Y_n(x) S_n(x)$$

Since $c_{2m,n}$ appear in the expansion of $\frac{x^{2n+1}}{\sinh^{2n+1} x}$, we deduce,

$$Y_n(x) = \sum_{r=0}^{\infty} y_{r,n} x^r = \sum_{r=0}^{\infty} c_{2r,n} \sqrt{x}^{2r} = \frac{\sqrt{x}^{2n+1}}{\sinh^{2n+1} \sqrt{x}}$$

The closed expression of the other series is found as follow

$$\begin{aligned}
 S_n(x) &= \sum_{r=0}^{\infty} s_{r,n} x^r \\
 &= \sum_{r=0}^{\infty} \frac{x^r}{(2r)!} \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \left\langle \begin{matrix} 2n \\ n-1-k \end{matrix} \right\rangle (2k+1)^{2r} \\
 &= \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \left\langle \begin{matrix} 2n \\ n-1-k \end{matrix} \right\rangle \sum_{r=0}^{\infty} \frac{((2k+1)^2 x)^r}{(2r)!} \\
 S_n(x) &= \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \left\langle \begin{matrix} 2n \\ n-1-k \end{matrix} \right\rangle \cosh((2k+1)\sqrt{x}).
 \end{aligned}$$

On using the definition of cosh, S_n looks like follow

$$S_n(x) = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \left\langle \begin{matrix} 2n \\ n-1-k \end{matrix} \right\rangle \left(e^{(2k+1)\sqrt{x}} + e^{-(2k+1)\sqrt{x}} \right)$$

On re-arranging each sum, we get

$$S_n(x) = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \left\langle \begin{matrix} 2n \\ k \end{matrix} \right\rangle e^{(2n-2k-1)\sqrt{x}} + \frac{1}{2} \sum_{k=n}^{2n-1} \left\langle \begin{matrix} 2n \\ 2n-1-k \end{matrix} \right\rangle e^{(2n-2k-1)\sqrt{x}}.$$

And on merging into one

$$S_n(x) = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{k=0}^{2n-1} \left\langle \begin{matrix} 2n \\ k \end{matrix} \right\rangle e^{(2n-1-2k)\sqrt{x}}.$$

A factorization yields

$$S_n(x) = \frac{1}{2} e^{(2n-1)\sqrt{x}} \sum_{k=0}^{2n-1} \left\langle \begin{matrix} 2n \\ k \end{matrix} \right\rangle e^{-2k\sqrt{x}}.$$

On using the common Eulerian polynomials, we have

$$S_n(x) = \frac{1}{2} e^{(2n-1)\sqrt{x}} A_{2n}(e^{-2\sqrt{x}}), \quad A_m(t) := \sum_{k=0}^{m-1} \left\langle \begin{matrix} m \\ k \end{matrix} \right\rangle t^k.$$

We make use of the generating function of Eulerian polynomials[10]

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} A_n(t) \frac{z^n}{n!} = \frac{t-1}{t-e^{(t-1)z}} = \frac{(1-t)e^{(1-t)z}}{1-te^{(1-t)z}}.$$

We identify as consequence formally

$$\frac{A_{2n}(e^{-2\sqrt{x}})}{(2n)!}$$

as the coefficient of z^{2n} in the Taylor expansion of

$$\frac{(1-e^{-2\sqrt{x}})e^{(1-e^{-2\sqrt{x}})z}}{1-e^{-2\sqrt{x}}e^{(1-e^{-2\sqrt{x}})z}}.$$

Hence,

$$S_n(x) = \frac{1}{2} e^{(2n-1)\sqrt{x}} (2n)! [z^{2n}] \frac{(1 - e^{-2\sqrt{x}}) e^{(1-e^{-2\sqrt{x}})z}}{1 - e^{-2\sqrt{x}} e^{(1-e^{-2\sqrt{x}})z}}.$$

On factorizing $1 - e^{-2\sqrt{x}}$,

$$S_n(x) = \frac{1}{2} e^{(2n-1)\sqrt{x}} (2n)! (1 - e^{-2\sqrt{x}}) [z^{2n}] \frac{e^{(1-e^{-2\sqrt{x}})z}}{1 - e^{-2\sqrt{x}} e^{(1-e^{-2\sqrt{x}})z}}.$$

On using the geometric series, we get

$$S_n(x) = \frac{1}{2} e^{(2n-1)\sqrt{x}} (2n)! (1 - e^{-2\sqrt{x}}) [z^{2n}] \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} \left(e^{-2\sqrt{x}} \right)^m e^{(m+1)(1-e^{-2\sqrt{x}})z}.$$

The coefficients of series being linear, hence

$$S_n(x) = \frac{1}{2} e^{(2n-1)\sqrt{x}} (2n)! (1 - e^{-2\sqrt{x}}) \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} \left(e^{-2\sqrt{x}} \right)^m [z^{2n}] e^{(m+1)(1-e^{-2\sqrt{x}})z}.$$

The formula $[t^n]e^{\alpha t} = \frac{\alpha^n}{n!}$, yields

$$\begin{aligned} S_n(x) &= \frac{1}{2} e^{(2n-1)\sqrt{x}} \left(1 - e^{-2\sqrt{x}} \right)^{2n+1} \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} (m+1)^{2n} e^{-2m\sqrt{x}} \\ &= \frac{1}{2} e^{-2\sqrt{x}} e^{(2n+1)\sqrt{x}} \left(1 - e^{-2\sqrt{x}} \right)^{2n+1} \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} (m+1)^{2n} e^{-2m\sqrt{x}} \end{aligned}$$

On writing with sinh, one gets

$$S_n(x) = 2^{2n} \sinh^{2n+1}(\sqrt{x}) \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} (m+1)^{2n} e^{-2(m+1)\sqrt{x}}$$

Going back to $g_{p,n}$ and using the formulae lead to

$$g_{p,n} = [x^{n-p}] \frac{\sqrt{x}^{2n+1}}{\sinh^{2n+1} \sqrt{x}} 2^{2n} \sinh^{2n+1}(\sqrt{x}) \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} (m+1)^{2n} e^{-2(m+1)\sqrt{x}}$$

Which reads

$$g_{p,n} = [x^{n-p}] x^n \sqrt{x} 2^{2n} \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} (m+1)^{2n} e^{-2(m+1)\sqrt{x}}$$

Or equivalently,

$$g_{p,n} = [x^{-p}] 2^{2n} \sqrt{x} \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} (m+1)^{2n} e^{-2(m+1)\sqrt{x}}$$

The linearity of the coefficient leads to

$$g_{p,n} = 2^{2n} \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} (m+1)^{2n} [x^{-p}] \sqrt{x} e^{-2(m+1)\sqrt{x}}$$

On using *Lemma 2*,

$$g_{p,n} = 2^{2n} \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} (m+1)^{2n} \operatorname{Res}_{s=p} \left(\int_0^{\infty} e^{-2(m+1)\sqrt{x}} \sqrt{x} x^{s-1} dx \right)$$

After the substitution $t = 2(m+1)\sqrt{x}$, $g_{p,n}$ takes the forms

$$\begin{aligned} g_{p,n} &= 2^{2n} \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} (m+1)^{2n} \operatorname{Res}_{s=p} \left(\frac{1}{2^{2s}(m+1)^{2s}} \int_0^{\infty} e^{-t} t^{2s} dt \right) \\ &= 2^{2n} \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} (m+1)^{2n} \operatorname{Res}_{s=p} \left(\frac{\Gamma(2s+1)}{2^{2s}(m+1)^{2s}} \right) \\ &= \operatorname{Res}_{s=p} \left(2^{2n} \Gamma(2s+1) \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} \frac{(m+1)^{2n}}{2^{2s}(m+1)^{2s}} \right) \\ &= \operatorname{Res}_{s=p} \left(2^{2n-2s} \Gamma(2s+1) \zeta(2s-2n) \right) \end{aligned}$$

- **Case** $p \in \llbracket 0, n-1 \rrbracket$

None of the functions 2^{2n-2s} , $\Gamma(2s+1)$ and $\zeta(2s-2n)$ has a pole when $p \in \llbracket 0, n-1 \rrbracket$. In the Mellin transform framework, only *simple* poles in s contribute residues. At $s = p < n$, what we see is not a *simple* pole of $\zeta(2s-2n)$ in s — the factor diverges to violently for every such p , not in a controlled Laurent expansion. The product $2^{2n-2s} \Gamma(2s+1) \zeta(2s-2n)$ does not show a *simple* pole structure here. The residue is as consequence 0. It follows

$$g_{p,n} = 0 \quad \text{if} \quad p \in \llbracket 0, n-1 \rrbracket$$

- **Case** $p = n$

$$g_{n,n} = \operatorname{Res}_{s=n} \left(2^{2n-2s} \Gamma(2s+1) \zeta(2s-2n) \right).$$

Write $s = n + \varepsilon$, with $\varepsilon \rightarrow 0^+$. Then

$$2^{2n-2s} = 2^{-2\varepsilon} = 1 - 2\varepsilon \ln 2 + O(\varepsilon^2),$$

and

$$\Gamma(2s+1) = \Gamma(2n+1+2\varepsilon) = (2n)! \left(1 + 2\varepsilon \psi(2n+1) + O(\varepsilon^2) \right),$$

where ψ is the digamma function.

For the zeta factor we keep its Dirichlet-series form:

$$\zeta(2s-2n) = \zeta(2\varepsilon) = \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} m^{-2\varepsilon}.$$

Expanding

$$m^{-2\varepsilon} = e^{-2\varepsilon \ln m} = 1 - 2\varepsilon \ln m + O(\varepsilon^2),$$

we obtain the asymptotics

$$\zeta(2\varepsilon) \sim \frac{1}{2\varepsilon} + O(1),$$

so that $\zeta(2\varepsilon)$ has a simple pole at $\varepsilon = 0$.

Combining these expansions gives

$$2^{2n-2s} \Gamma(2s+1) \zeta(2s-2n) \sim (2n)! \left(\frac{1}{2\varepsilon} + O(1) \right).$$

Therefore the residue at $s = n$ is

$$g_{n,n} = \frac{(2n)!}{2}$$

in agreement with the combinatorial evaluation.

Theorem 5:

$$\forall n \in \mathbb{N}^*,$$

$$\text{Let } a_{p,n} := \sum_{m=0}^{n-p} \frac{d_{2m,n}}{(2n-2m-2p)!} \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \left\langle \begin{matrix} 2n-1 \\ k \end{matrix} \right\rangle^B (2n-1-2k)^{2n-2m-2p}$$

$$\text{Then } a_{p,n} = \begin{cases} \frac{2^{2n-2}(2^{2n-1}-1)B_{2n}}{n}, & p = 0, \\ 0, & p \in \llbracket 1, n-1 \rrbracket, \\ 2^{2n-2}(2n-1)!, & p = n. \end{cases}$$

Proof:

We let

$$a_{p,n} := \sum_{m=0}^{n-p} \frac{d_{2m,n}}{(2n-2m-2p)!} \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \left\langle \begin{matrix} 2n-1 \\ k \end{matrix} \right\rangle^B (2n-1-2k)^{2n-2m}$$

On letting

$$h_{m,n} := d_{2m,n} \quad \text{and} \quad t_{r,n} := \frac{1}{(2r)!} \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \left\langle \begin{matrix} 2n-1 \\ k \end{matrix} \right\rangle^B (2n-1-2k)^{2r}$$

We become

$$a_{p,n} = \sum_{m=0}^{n-p} h_{m,n} t_{n-m-p,n}$$

This last expression $a_{p,n}$ is exactly the form of coefficients arising in the Cauchy product formula. As consequence, $a_{p,n}$ is the coefficient of x^{n-p} appearing in the Cauchy product of the series generated by the coefficients $h_{m,n}$ and $t_{m,n}$. On considering

$$H_n(x) := \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} h_{m,n} x^m \quad \text{and} \quad T_n(x) := \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} t_{m,n} x^m$$

we formalize the writing of $a_{p,n}$ in following manner :

$$a_{p,n} = [x^{n-p}] H_n(x) T_n(x)$$

Now

$$\sum_{m=0}^{\infty} d_{m,n} x^m = \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} d_{2m,n} x^{2m} = \frac{x^{2n}}{\sinh^{2n} x}$$

according to the definition of the coefficients $b_{m,n}$ and $d_{m,n}$ introduced in Paragraph §2 of Section 3.

We deduce

$$H_n(x) = \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} h_{m,n} x^m = \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} d_{2m,n} x^m = \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} d_{2m,n} (\sqrt{x})^{2m} = \frac{\sqrt{x}^{2n}}{\sinh^{2n} \sqrt{x}} = \frac{x^n}{\sinh^{2n} \sqrt{x}}$$

The closed form of $T_n(x)$ being harder to find, is found by paying attention to the following steps

$$\begin{aligned} t_{r,n} &:= \frac{1}{(2r)!} \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \left\langle \begin{matrix} 2n-1 \\ k \end{matrix} \right\rangle^B (2n-1-2k)^{2r} \\ T_n(x) &:= \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} t_{m,n} x^m \\ T_n(x) &= \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} \frac{x^m}{(2m)!} \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \left\langle \begin{matrix} 2n-1 \\ k \end{matrix} \right\rangle^B (2n-1-2k)^{2m} \\ &= \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \left\langle \begin{matrix} 2n-1 \\ k \end{matrix} \right\rangle^B \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} \frac{((2n-1-2k)^2 x)^m}{(2m)!} \\ &= \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \left\langle \begin{matrix} 2n-1 \\ k \end{matrix} \right\rangle^B \cosh(\sqrt{x} (2n-1-2k)) \\ &= \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \left\langle \begin{matrix} 2n-1 \\ k \end{matrix} \right\rangle^B \cosh((2n-1-2k)\sqrt{x}) \\ T_n(x) &= \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \left\langle \begin{matrix} 2n-1 \\ k \end{matrix} \right\rangle^B \cosh((2n-1-2k)\sqrt{x}) \end{aligned}$$

On expanding cosh by exponential functions, we get

$$T_n(x) = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \left\langle \begin{matrix} 2n-1 \\ k \end{matrix} \right\rangle^B \left(e^{(2n-1-2k)\sqrt{x}} + e^{-(2n-1-2k)\sqrt{x}} \right)$$

Which reads

$$T_n(x) = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \left\langle \begin{matrix} 2n-1 \\ k \end{matrix} \right\rangle^B e^{(2n-1-2k)\sqrt{x}} + \frac{1}{2} \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \left\langle \begin{matrix} 2n-1 \\ k \end{matrix} \right\rangle^B e^{-(2n-1-2k)\sqrt{x}}$$

On re-indexing and reversing the order of summation of the second sum,

$$T_n(x) = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \left\langle \begin{matrix} 2n-1 \\ k \end{matrix} \right\rangle^B e^{(2n-1-2k)\sqrt{x}} + \frac{1}{2} \sum_{k=n}^{2n-1} \left\langle \begin{matrix} 2n-1 \\ 2n-1-k \end{matrix} \right\rangle^B e^{(2n-1-2k)\sqrt{x}}$$

On recalling the symmetry of Eulerian numbers of type B, we merge into one

$$T_n(x) = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{k=0}^{2n-1} \left\langle \begin{matrix} 2n-1 \\ k \end{matrix} \right\rangle^B e^{(2n-1-2k)\sqrt{x}}$$

We use the typ-B Eulerian Polynomials defined as

$$B_m(z) := \sum_{k=0}^m \left\langle \begin{matrix} m \\ k \end{matrix} \right\rangle^B z^k.$$

As result,

$$T_n(x) = \frac{1}{2} e^{(2n-1)\sqrt{x}} B_{2n-1}(e^{-2\sqrt{x}}).$$

One has the generating function[11][12]

$$\sum_{m=0}^{\infty} B_m(z) \frac{t^m}{m!} = \frac{(1-z)e^{(1-z)t}}{1-ze^{2(1-z)t}}$$

We identify formally

$$\frac{B_{2n-1}(e^{-2\sqrt{x}})}{(2n-1)!}$$

as the coefficient of t^{2n-1} in the Taylor expansion around 0 of

$$\frac{(1-e^{-2\sqrt{x}})e^{(1-e^{-2\sqrt{x}})t}}{1-e^{-2\sqrt{x}}e^{2(1-e^{-2\sqrt{x}})t}}.$$

As consequence

$$T_n(x) = \frac{1}{2} e^{(2n-1)\sqrt{x}} (2n-1)! [t^{2n-1}] \frac{(1-e^{-2\sqrt{x}})e^{(1-e^{-2\sqrt{x}})t}}{1-e^{-2\sqrt{x}}e^{2(1-e^{-2\sqrt{x}})t}}.$$

The term $1-e^{-2\sqrt{x}}$ is factored out since it does not depends on t .

$$T_n(x) = \frac{1}{2} (1-e^{-2\sqrt{x}}) e^{(2n-1)\sqrt{x}} (2n-1)! [t^{2n-1}] \frac{e^{(1-e^{-2\sqrt{x}})t}}{1-e^{-2\sqrt{x}}e^{2(1-e^{-2\sqrt{x}})t}}.$$

On using the geometric series, we get

$$T_n(x) = \frac{1}{2} (1-e^{-2\sqrt{x}}) e^{(2n-1)\sqrt{x}} (2n-1)! [t^{2n-1}] \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} e^{-2m\sqrt{x}} e^{(1-e^{-2\sqrt{x}})(2m+1)t}.$$

The coefficients in series are linear, hence

$$T_n(x) = \frac{1}{2} (1-e^{-2\sqrt{x}}) e^{(2n-1)\sqrt{x}} (2n-1)! \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} e^{-2m\sqrt{x}} [t^{2n-1}] e^{(1-e^{-2\sqrt{x}})(2m+1)t}$$

The formula $[t^n]e^{\alpha t} = \frac{\alpha^n}{n!}$, yields

$$T_n(x) = \frac{1}{2} (1-e^{-2\sqrt{x}}) e^{(2n-1)\sqrt{x}} \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} e^{-2m\sqrt{x}} \left((1-e^{-2\sqrt{x}})(2m+1) \right)^{2n-1}.$$

The term $1 - e^{-2\sqrt{x}}$ is independent of m and is factored out

$$T_n(x) = \frac{1}{2} (1 - e^{-2\sqrt{x}})^{2n} e^{(2n-1)\sqrt{x}} \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} (2m+1)^{2n-1} e^{-2m\sqrt{x}}.$$

The outer term is treated to yield \sinh in the final expression as follow

$$T_n(x) = 2^{2n-1} \sinh^{2n}(\sqrt{x}) \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} (2m+1)^{2n-1} e^{-(2m+1)\sqrt{x}}.$$

On using the closed expressions of $H_n(x)$ and $T_n(x)$, $a_{p,n}$ takes the form

$$a_{p,n} = [x^{n-p}] \frac{x^n}{\sinh^{2n} \sqrt{x}} 2^{2n-1} e^{-\sqrt{x}} \sinh^{2n}(\sqrt{x}) \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} (2m+1)^{2n-1} e^{-2m\sqrt{x}}$$

On simplifying,

$$a_{p,n} = [x^{n-p}] x^n 2^{2n-1} \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} (2m+1)^{2n-1} e^{-(2m+1)\sqrt{x}}$$

The formula $[x^y]x^z f(x) = [x^{y-z}]f(x)$ and the linearity of the coefficient yield

$$a_{p,n} = 2^{2n-1} \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} (2m+1)^{2n-1} [x^{-p}] e^{-(2m+1)\sqrt{x}}$$

On using the formula of coefficients through Mellin's transforms (Lemma 2), one obtains

$$a_{p,n} = 2^{2n-1} \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} (2m+1)^{2n-1} \operatorname{Res}_{s=p} \mathcal{M} \left[e^{-(2m+1)\sqrt{x}} \right]$$

Which reads

$$a_{p,n} = 2^{2n-1} \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} (2m+1)^{2n-1} \operatorname{Res}_{s=p} \left(\int_0^{\infty} e^{-(2m+1)\sqrt{x}} x^{s-1} dx \right)$$

The substitution $t = (2m+1)\sqrt{x}$ yields

$$a_{p,n} = 2^{2n-1} \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} (2m+1)^{2n-1} \operatorname{Res}_{s=p} \left(\frac{2}{(2m+1)^{2s}} \int_0^{\infty} e^{-t} t^{2s-1} dt \right)$$

One recognizes the last integral as the Gamma function. As implication

$$\begin{aligned} a_{p,n} &= 2^{2n-1} \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} (2m+1)^{2n-1} \operatorname{Res}_{s=p} \left(\frac{2 \Gamma(2s)}{(2m+1)^{2s}} \right) \\ &= \operatorname{Res}_{s=p} \left(2^{2n-1} \cdot 2 \Gamma(2s) \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} \frac{(2m+1)^{2n-1}}{(2m+1)^{2s}} \right) \end{aligned}$$

The last series is rewritten with the Riemann zeta function as follow

$$a_{p,n} = \operatorname{Res}_{s=p} \left(2^{2n} \Gamma(2s) \left(1 - 2^{-(2s-2n+1)} \right) \zeta(2s - 2n + 1) \right)$$

- **Case** $p = 0$

$\Gamma(2s)$ has a simple pole at $s = 0$ with Laurent expansion :

$$\Gamma(2s) = \frac{1}{2s} - \gamma + \dots$$

the residue of $\Gamma(2s)$ for $s = 0$ is then $\frac{1}{2}$. The term $(1 - 2^{-(2s-2n+1)}) \zeta(2s - 2n + 1)$ is regular and does not have any pole at all. As consequence

$$a_{0,n} = 2^{2n-1} (1 - 2^{2n-1}) \zeta(1 - 2n)$$

And on using the functional equation of ζ in combination with the exact values of $\zeta(2n)$, we conclude

$$a_{0,n} = - \frac{2^{2n-1} (1 - 2^{2n-1})}{2n} B_{2n}$$

- **Case** $p \in \llbracket 1, n - 1 \rrbracket$

None of the functions $(1 - 2^{-(2s-2n+1)})$, $\zeta(2s - 2n + 1)$ and $\Gamma(2s)$ has a pole at $s = p$ when $p \in \llbracket 1, n - 1 \rrbracket$. In the Mellin transform framework, only *simple* poles in s contribute residues. At $s = p \in \llbracket 1, n - 1 \rrbracket$, what we see is not a *simple* pole of $\zeta(2s - 2n + 1)$ in s — the factor diverges to violently for every such p . The product $2^{2n-2s} \Gamma(2s + 1) \zeta(2s - 2n)$ does not show a *simple* pole structure here at $s = p$. The residue holds then a zero value in this case. Formally,

$$a_{p,n} = 0 \quad \text{if} \quad p \in \llbracket 1, n - 1 \rrbracket$$

- **Case** $p = n$

$\Gamma(2s)$ is regular with value $(2n - 1)!$, $(1 - 2^{-(2s-2n+1)})$ is regular too with value $\frac{1}{2}$. But $\zeta(2s - 2n + 1)$ has a simple pole since $\zeta(1)$ is in fact the *harmonic series*. And Around $s = n$, one has indeed the Taylor expansion

$$\zeta(1 + 2(s - n)) = \frac{1}{2(s - n)} + \gamma + \dots$$

So, the residue is $\frac{1}{2}$. It follows

$$a_{n,n} = 2^{2n-2} (2n - 1)!$$

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